

Granulomatous Mastitis; A Diagnostic Burden in the Breast Clinic

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SUMMARY

This case report aims to highlight both the varied clinical presentation/challenges of diagnosis as well as the challenges of choosing from the options of management for granulomatous mastitis. One of the cases was initially thought to be a breast abscess while the other was thought to be a benign breast lesion, with both ultimately diagnosed as granulomatous mastitis after several sets of investigations, visits to the breast specialist and discussions at the breast MDT. Corynebacterium specie being implicated like in some of the literature reviews. Treatment of the cases highlighted were predominantly conservative, with satisfactory patient outcomes

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BACKGROUND

Granulomatous mastitis (GM) is a rare, chronic benign inflammatory breast condition. It often presents a diagnostic challenge and can mimic common breast conditions such as a carcinoma, infective mastitis, or breast abscess. It causes significant morbidity for the affected cases in the form of physical, mental, psychological stress.

The clinical presentation is variable, usually affecting women in childbearing age, mostly with a history of breastfeeding [1,2]. Patients may present with progressively enlarging breast lumps of variable sizes that are firm, tender, and unilateral. Sometimes, it can be fixed to the skin causing nipple retraction or fixed to underlying pectoralis muscle. The radiological finding of granulomatous mastitis is of an ill-defined mass that is difficult to distinguish from that of carcinoma and other granulomatous diseases. The frequent findings on mammogram and ultrasound scan (USS) are asymmetric, diffuse, increased density, hypoechoic mass lesions, or nodular structures. The aetiology is multiple and can be infectious or non-infectious. Idiopathic granulomatous mastitis (IGM) or lobular granulomatous mastitis (granulomatous lobulitis) is a rare non-infectious chronic granulomatous inflammatory process that was first described in 1972. It is considered more likely that there is secondary infection of the breasts in most cases, even when the presumed primary focus is clinically in-apparent [2].

Since the clinical presentation can mimic infectious mastitis or inflammatory carcinoma, the disease often runs a protracted course. The diagnosis is made by histopathology. Biopsies show a granulomatous formation in combination with a localized infiltration of multi-nucleated giant cells, epithelioid histiocytes, lymphocytes, eosinophils, neutrophils, and plasma cells [1,2]. Ultrasound, mammography, and magnetic resonance imaging are not specific; however, ultrasound and mammography should be done to exclude other pathologies [1]. Due to the lack of data including randomized controlled studies, the management of GM is controversial. Most authors have indicated therapy regimen starting with antibiotics and corticosteroids, followed by continuous steroid therapy and surgery in patients with persisting symptoms [1].

CASE PRESENTATION

Case 1:

Female in her early 40s with BMI of 44 who first presented couple of years back with progressive right breast pain and swelling associated with nipple discharge. Pain radiated to the right arm. Patient had history of three episodes of mastitis while breastfeeding; she had breastfed a couple years prior to presentation. She had a previous attendance to the breast clinic for nipple discharge following a diagnosis of pituitary adenoma.

She received a course of flucloxacillin from her GP before presenting to the emergency department for worsening of symptoms-examination of the breast revealed a right breast inferio-lateral erythema and induration with retracted nipple but no discharge. There was a large area (15×8cm) of induration in right breast with no obvious fluctuance or abscess formation. There was no axillary lymphadenopathy. Patient was treated conservatively with antibiotics and analgesia, before being referred to the breast clinic.

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Clinical examination in the clinic revealed C/D–cup breasts having an erythematous area stretching over the lateral pole and extending onto the medial side of the right breast-additionally there was an underlying well-delineated and palpable 8-10 cm sized lump.

Case 2:

Female in her late 20s, with a BMI of 60 and allergic to penicillin. Couple years ago, she attended the breast clinic for the first time with a lump in her left breast of 4-5 months duration. The lump slightly increased in size. No family history of breast or ovarian cancer. She had her menarche at the age of 13 and had regular periods. She had been using contraceptive pills for the last 12 years. She had B-cup sized breasts and on clinical assessment, there was a 2-cm lump at 11 o'clock position in the left breast, which felt benign on examination.

INVESTIGATIONS

Case 1:

She had several breast Ultrasounds to assess the extent of the pathology, to guide biopsy/drainage and to monitor the collection. She also had a mammography on two separate occasions to evaluate the possibility of a malignant transformation. Imaging findings are as highlighted below.

Case 2:

She had a couple of ultrasounds for assessment and monitoring. Relevant imaging reports discussed below.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Case 1:

Due to a background history of mastitis during breastfeeding months prior to presentation, the initial diagnosis entertained was a recurrent mastitis. However, due to the persistence/worsening of symptoms further investigations were carried out especially to rule out a malignancy. Whilst Physical examination revealed aforementioned findings, there was no regional lymphadenopathy. Mammographic findings and biopsy showed no evidence of malignancy either. GM was arrived at following biopsy findings of granulomatous inflammation and cultures revealing the offending bacteria of interest.

Case 2:

The initial diagnosis was a fibrocystic change in the breast or a fibroadenoma. Though it was considered a benign lesion, recurrence necessitated further investigations as well, leading to the diagnosis of GM.

TREATMENT

Case 1:

Mammogram (Figure 1) confirmed a swelling in the right breast with the appearances of a chronic abscess, whilst the ultrasound scan of the corresponding area showed a 52mm x 15mm collection within a well-formed swelling (Figure 2). An attempted aspiration yielded a small amount of thick fluid which was sent for culture and sensitivity. Skin punch biopsy showed no evidence of neoplasia; however, there was evidence of some granulomatous inflammation. Breast multidisciplinary team (MDT) discussion advised TB PCR test, which turned to be negative. The patient had multiple clinic visits afterwards with multiple repeated USS which showed some improvement in the collection, as seen for example in Figure 3. The patient had multiple attempts at aspirations and cultures with varying results- no growth to one showing only coagulase negative staphylococcus, and finally organisms were identified on the last culture. Later, cultures revealed heavy growth of *Corynebacterium* species identified as *Corynebacterium Kroppenstedtii* (CK) and heavy growth of *Bacillus megaterium* identified as *Priestia megaterium* with sensitivity to clindamycin. Patient was commenced on clindamycin resulting in significant symptomatic relief. A year later, she had developed patchy areas of redness at 1 o'clock on the right breast, with areas of erythema and induration at 9 o'clock and a small sinus discharging sanguineous pus (Figure 4). Weeks after this, further collections and sinuses were noted (Figure 5). However, she was managed conservatively because she was systematically well and there was significant resolution of symptoms, with US revealing an improvement in the residual collection.

Few months later, the patient presented with new findings in the other breast. She is currently on follow-up to monitor both breasts.

Case 2:

USS showed a 23x19mm ovoid well-defined mass with shadowing and mixed internal contents and peripheral vascularity only (Figure 6). Biopsy revealed no cyst or fibro-epithelial lesion. There were no features suggestive of malignancy. The biopsy was coded as B2 due to the presence of stromal fibrosis and micro-calcification. Breast MDT discussion concluded a benign lesion for re-assurance and discharge from clinic.

Patient's symptoms didn't resolve, and patient presented herself to clinic again. Repeat USS showed a 31x17 mm area of inflammation with mixed internal echoes appearances suggest a resolving abscess (Figure 7). The patient was treated with antibiotics but with no signs of resolution. Another attendance to the breast clinic with pain and erythema in the left breast close to the nipple

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areolar complex revealed induration and thickening but overall benign feeling. Repeat USS showed abscess had reduced in size to 25x16x10mm. The patient was prescribed antibiotics and a followup clinic arranged.

Several months from the first attendance, the patient presented once more to the breast clinic with recurrence of the breast lump that made her wake up from sleep due to sharp, stabbing pain. No associated systemic manifestation.

On clinical examination, she had a tender lump, deep in the peri-areolar area of the left breast. It didn't appear to be acute. USS revealed a 49x22mm lesion, consistent with an abscess, with most of the collection not liquefied (Figure 8). About 2-3cc of thick pus was aspirated and sent for microbiology. Mildly raised CRP, normal WCC. Pus culture revealed pus cells with no isolated organisms; However, heavy growth of Diphtheroids was isolated after an extended period of incubation.

The patient attended the clinic again a month later with complaints of tenderness around the area and difficulty wearing a bra. On clinical examination, there was a persistent 3-4 cm tender looking lump deep in the left breast in the upper pole, just lateral to nipple areolar complex. Breast MDT discussion concluded chronic granulomatous mastitis with Diphtheroid growth.

The patient though remains systemically well. Most recent follow-up USS showed some residual chronic inflammatory changes (Figure 9); limited aspiration done by radiologist, with fluid sent for culture, grew some bacillus species with no significant growth or sensitivity. There were no concerns on examination, and plan is to continue conservative management with no need for antibiotics.

OUTCOME AND FOLLOW-UP

Case 1:

Later, the patient developed a collection in her left breast. Ultrasound revealed ill-defined area of increased echogenicity, consistent with mastitis/inflammatory changes which measured 43x21mm (Figure 10). No findings in the scan to suggest drainable collection. Initially planned to for Ultrasound guided core biopsy of the area. However, on a background of similar morphological findings in the right breast, it was decided to treat with antibiotics and anti-inflammatory and monitor response clinically and radiologically with a follow-up ultrasound scan in 4 weeks. The follow-up scan showed duct ectasia only in the left peri-areolar region, with no suspicious features, evidence of inflammation or discrete collection. A repeat scan showed a collection 65x33mm extending towards the retro areolar region, consistent with an abscess. US-guided aspiration revealed thick pus. Sample sent for microbiological analysis. Post-aspiration patient confirmed that the area of concern in the left breast felt much smaller and better. She was started on Clindamycin.

Case 2:

One year follow-up revealed no new concerns.

DISCUSSION

There is no valid incidence and prevalent data of GM from Europe. Most of the publications come from the Middle East, Mediterranean countries, Asia, and the USA, and as such highlight a higher prevalence of GM among women from those region [1]. However, both women in our report are British Caucasians.

GM was first described as a distinct clinical entity by Kessler and Wolloch in 1972 [1, 3]. Going et al. put forward the term granulomatous lobular mastitis in a bid to separate this lesion from the granulomatous form of periductal mastitis [4]. However, to differentiate between these two conditions, a large specimen is necessary to detect specific changes implying the localization of inflammation [5]. For our case report, we adopted the term granulomatous mastitis (GM).

Multiple inflammatory breast diseases are deemed to be the result of a cascade of an initial insult to the ductal epithelial cells in the breast which causes a transition of luminal secretions to the lobular stroma. This may cause a local inflammatory response in the connective tissue that recruits macrophages and lymphocytes to the affected region, culminating in a local granulomatous response. These inflammatory breast diseases namely IGM, periductal mastitis and mammary duct ectasia, have been posited to belong to a heterogeneous group of entities termed mammary duct-associated inflammatory disease sequence (MDAIDS) which was introduced by Meguid et al. [5]. According to the concept of MDAIDS, certain conditions, such as pregnancy, breast-feeding, and drug-induced hyperprolactinemia or galactorrhoea, might be associated with an increased risk of GM [5,6]. Other possible aetiopathogenesis include inflammatory response to trauma, metabolic or hormonal processes and autoimmunity [1]. Whilst case one had hyperprolactinemia from a pituitary adenoma, case two had been on the pill for about 12 years, which could account for some hormonal interference, as it has also been postulated that the use of oral contraceptives could be a risk factor [7].

Recently, infectious factors have been increasingly implicated in the pathogenesis of GM. Studies have focused on the relationship between infection and GM, especially *Corynebacterium* species. However, it is neither clear the role this bacterium plays in the onset of GM, nor the extent of the relationship between bacterial infection and clinical manifestation [8]. At the species level, *Corynebacterium kroppenstedtii* (CK) was the predominant species in several studies. Bi et al. [9] in their study using next-generation sequencing on 25 GM patients' samples found CK in 40% of them, while Chen et al, 2023 [8] identified CK as the predominant species in 88.2% of *Corynebacterium*-positive and *Corynebacterium*-dominant GM samples. In our case one, CK was isolated after multiple cultures, whereas in case two, Diphtheroids were isolated in the culture. It is not uncommon to find

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Corynebacterium in normal breast tissues. As such, whether Corynebacterium is a colonizer, contaminant, or pathogen has been argued for years. In normal breast tissue, however, the Corynebacterium abundance is generally <0.5% [8].

GM usually occurs in women in reproductive age, approximately 2–6 years after delivery [1,8]. In the first case, patient presented with symptoms 3 years after stopping breast feeding on a background of recurrent mastitis whilst breastfeeding. Bear in mind that milk stasis can exist for several years after weaning, and also, elevated prolactin levels can stimulate ducts to oversecrete [8,10]. This can induce mammary duct dilation, chronic inflammation and local immune response. In addition, the residual milk in the mammary duct provides a rich media for the lipophilic Corynebacterium organism [8].

Granted that a good number of GM cases show association with lactation and pregnancy, a few have been linked to hyperprolactinemia from use of dopamine antagonist medications or from intracranial lesions, such as pituitary adenoma [10]. This was the possible aetiology in case one who was under endocrinologists for pituitary adenoma with symptomatic relief of coinciding with reduction in prolactin following treatment of hyperprolactinaemia.

Unilateral involvement of the breasts is typical, although bilateral disease has been described [1,7]. Whilst both cases in our report were extra-areolar, it is noteworthy that in the second case, it was more peri-areolar and there was nipple retraction noted in both; however, there were no lymphadenopathies in either case.

The treatment options that have been advocated include surgical excision, use of steroids and more commonly drainage of abscess along with antibiotics. While some investigators have reported considerable success with steroids [11], most have reported a considerable risk of recurrence and are wary of the long-term side effect profile of steroid use. Lai et al. advocated expectant management with close regular surveillance as the treatment of choice [12]. Both our cases had antibiotics, with the first case getting prolactin reducing medication, as well.

GM represents a significant morbidity and distress to the patient, complexity to the doctor, and makes considerable demands on the medical system resources. For the patient, the journey to diagnose can be long and seemingly inefficient, not to mention the stigmata and scarring it may leave behind after all said and done.

Over the course of the last 16 months; from her initial presentation to the breast clinic to her latest clinic visit, case one has had about 20 breast clinic visits, 2 mammograms, 15 US scans, 2 biopsies and several swabs/cultures; this is not including, breast specialist nurses' involvements/calls, GP and ED visits from the onset of symptoms. Case two had been in contact with the breast team for over a year with 5 clinic visits, 5 US scans, multiple swabs and cultures too; this also does not include initial visits to the GP and ED. GM is indeed a condition involving multiple clinic visits, imaging, biopsies, swabs and cultures.

Therefore, we would like to recommend establishing a registry for GM cases to reach an algorithm for diagnosis and management. Secondly, the patients usually have many clinic visits and a longer term follow-up, early referral of affected cases to support groups within the health organization could be beneficial.

LEARNING POINTS/TAKE HOME MESSAGES

- GM is a rare inflammatory disease of the breast that can clinically mimic malignancy and/or other inflammatory breast conditions.
- None of the cases were diagnosed clinically and radiologically until biopsy, which emphasizes the need for awareness among surgeons, radiologists, and pathologists of this unusual but distinctive disorder.
- There is no one option of management and as such, treatment is individualised to the patient drawing from a knowledge of their pros and cons.
- The disease toll on the patient; physically, psychologically and otherwise must be considered and help recruited when indicated for these patients.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1: Mammogram showing scattered areas of fibro-glandular density. Increased asymmetry in the right upper central aspect, findings could be in keeping with chronic abscess.

Figure 2: US showing Increased echogenicity seen throughout the quadrant, with an apparent thickened collection measuring at least 52x15mm just below the skin surface.

Figure 3: Features suggest a resolving collection within the skin and measures 56mm in maximum dimension.

Figure 4: Clinical state of right breast 7 months from first presentation.

Figure 5: Multiple areas (at least 4) of patchy new collection in UIQ - largest 32x5mm.

Figure 6: 23x19mm ovoid well defined mass in the left breast at the 11-12 o'clock position with shadowing and mixed internal contents; peripheral vascularity only.

Figure 7: At 11-12 o'clock position, there is a 31x17mm area of persistent inflammation with mixed internal echo collection suggestive of resolving abscess.

Figure 8: UOQ reveals lesion of size 49x22 mm, consistent with abscess; Most of it appears not liquefied; persistent and increased in size from previous scan.

Figure 9: Post-aspiration US from last aspiration. 24x20mm heterogeneous area, with 2.5mls of lightyellow milky abscess fluid aspirated and residual mass of 19mm.

Figure 10: 43x21 mm ill-defined area of increased echogenicity, consistent with mastitis/inflammatory changes.

PATIENT'S PERSPECTIVE

Case 1 Patient's Perspective

Couple of years back, I started to feel some pain in my right breast and could feel 2 lumps forming. I had felt this previously when breastfeeding, as I had mastitis several times, but as I had not breastfed for 4 years, I was concerned so went to my GP. They felt the lumps and said to monitor them and if they got worse, then go to A&E department over the weekend. The swelling in my right breast got much worse over the weekend, so I ended up going to A&E department, as my breast had become hard as a rock and I was in excruciating pain, I was seen by one of the doctors, who called the breast surgeon on call that morning over, who gave me some codeine for the pain and put an urgent referral in for me to the breast clinic.

At this time, I was struggling to do anything due to the amount of pain I was in, and I didn't know where to put myself. My husband had to take over caring for our son, as I just had to lay down with heat on it and supporting it. I found it difficult to get comfortable while sleeping and when I rolled over in my sleep and laid on the breast, I woke up crying. I was seen that week by a breast consultant, who sent me for an ultrasound and a mammogram. Having a mammogram while my breast was so swollen was beyond any pain I have ever felt. I felt like my breast was going to explode.

During the ultrasound, they found some collections of thick fluid that seemed to be attached to the skin beneath my nipple. I felt relieved that it wasn't a tumour, but also concerned as to what could be causing it.

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I was prescribed antibiotics for 2 weeks. These started to help, but then within a week of finishing the course, the lumps and infection came back, so I was back into clinic for more tests and scans and put on more antibiotics. The biopsies were painful and uncomfortable, and I had to take time off work after one of them due to the pain I was in. I felt extremely anxious during this time of constantly having to go back and forth with them nearly every 3 weeks, and not knowing what was causing it, as you fear the worst. While I was extremely well supported by the consultant and staff at the hospital, and every effort was made, there remained a growing frustration that a cause could not be found.

During this time, the infection came to the surface and formed a raised welt under my skin, which then burst. I had days of infection oozing out of the wound and had to have dressings on, changing them 3-4 times a day due to the amount of oozing out. I felt extremely run-down from the initial antibiotics but was then put on a much stronger course. These ones really knocked me for six, and I had a constant metallic taste in my mouth for the full 3 weeks of taking them. At this point, it was taking a toll on my mental health, and I was feeling extremely down and depressed and drained, and just wanted it to be over or to be told what it was and why it kept coming back.

As I was getting to the point of my right breast clearing up and not recurring, my left breast flared up and I went in and was put straight on the same antibiotics that cleared the right breast up, and that has not come back. This was a great relief, as I expected another prolonged battle. The constant ultrasounds and biopsies and general pain and discomfort for the last year has taken a toll on me, and I keep expecting it to come back, with every tinge or slight lumpiness in either breast makes me think it is happening again, and I will be back on the rollercoaster or scans, tests and antibiotics. While I am lucky to have been well supported at work and have been allowed time to attend all hospital appointments, I am also concerned that if the condition were to flare up again in a significant way, it would have an impact on my employment.

Case 2 Patient's Perspective

Upon finding the lump, I straight away got a doctor's appointment. The process of referral to the clinic was very quick. Everyone at the clinic was very nice and professional. The biopsy went well, but I was very shaken afterwards. The results were received very quickly, which eased my worries. The development of the abscess following the biopsy was a bit frustrating, but again, was dealt with quickly and professionally. The lump is still present and causes me discomfort. If being involved in this study can help other people, I am happy to help.

Mammogram showing scattered areas of fibro-glandular density. Increased asymmetry in the right upper central aspect, findings could be in keeping with chronic abscess. (Sept. 2022).

26x32mm (300 x 300 DPI)

US showing Increased echogenicity seen throughout the quadrant, with an apparent thickened collection measuring at least 52x15mm just below the skin surface. (Sept 2022).
26x18mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Features suggest a resolving collection within the skin and measures 56mm in maximum dimension. (Nov. 2022).
54x37mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Clinical state of right breast 7 months from first presentation. (April 2023)
24x11mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Multiple areas (at least 4) of patchy new collection in UIQ - largest 32x5mm. (June 2023).
26x18mm (300 x 300 DPI)

23x19mm ovoid well defined mass in the left breast at the 11-12 o'clock position with shadowing and mixed internal contents; peripheral vascularity only. (Feb. 2022)
26x18 mm(300x300 DPI)

At 11-12 o'clock position, there is a 31x17mm area of persistent inflammation with mixed internal echo collection suggestive of resolving abscess. (Aug. 2022).

26x18mm (300 x 300 DPI)

UOQ reveals lesion of size 49x22 mm, consistent with abscess; Most of it appears not liquefied; persistent and increased in size from previous scan. (Oct. 2022)

26x18mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Post-aspiration US from last aspiration. 24x20mm heterogeneous area, with 2.5mls of light-yellow milky abscess fluid aspirated and residual mass of 19mm. (Jan 2023).

26x18mm (300 x 300 DPI)

43x21 mm ill-defined area of increased echogenicity, consistent with mastitis/inflammatory changes. (Sept 2023)

34x31mm (300 x 300 DPI)